
Paper 9
**MEASURES TO PREVENT CRIME AGAINST WOMEN
IN INDIA**

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Abstract:

Rigveda depicts women with highest respect in the Indian society. Volumes can be written on the heroic deeds of Indian women since from Vedic to modern times. But the social, political and economic changes lead towards the deterioration of women status. Many evil customs and traditions stepped in which enslaved the women and tied them to the boundaries of the house. The official statistics recorded declining sex-ratio, health status, literacy rate, work participation rate and political participation. Other hand, social evils including dowry deaths, child marriages, domestic violence, rape, sexual harassment and exploitation started to spread in the society. New evils including humiliation, rape, kidnapping, molestation, honor killing, torture abuse started to spread. The society which cannot respect, protect and nurture its women and children loses moral moorings running adrift. The plight of women is not likely to change as the time started to watch helplessly the suffering of women in the form of discrimination, oppression, exploitation, degradation, aggression and humiliation. India patriarchal system has suppressed and subjugated the women's life to a greater extent. Indian society believed clinging on to the orthodox beliefs causing brunt of violence in the form of public, physical, emotional and moral damages. Violence against women has become the world wide phenomena. This paper review about various forms of crimes committed against women, the strategies to curb these evils, future prospective to empower women to contribute to the national growth.

Keywords: Women, Crime, Violence, Exploitation, Humiliation, Orthodox, Empowerment.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Indian society considers women as the second class citizens even though we represent goddesses like Durga, Saraswati, Parvati and Kali to women. Women face the problems in acceptance due to the male dominant society which resulted in the deterioration of their status. Even though women devotes their life towards family are not able to get share in the parental property, medical care and education depriving their equality. Indian Constitution guarantees women with equality, dignity and protection from exploitation. Poverty demands women's participation in economic activities. History of India replicates women status as high in the ancient times, low in the medieval period, equal during reformatory ages varying with time. Violence against women gets social sanction from the gender superiority prevailing in the society men superior over women. The semantic meaning of crime is causing direct or indirect physical or mental cruelty to women such as Child marriages, infanticide, Sati, Sexual harassment, Dowry, physical aggressions, physical abuse, hanging, trafficking, intimidation, stalking, abuse, female genital mutilation, eve-teasing, rape, mental pressure, battering, maltreatment, cohesion, blackmails, emotional threats, control over speech and actions, domestic violence, eve-teasing, molestation, bigamy, fraudulent marriage, adultery,

cruelty, abduction of married women, kidnapping, harassment at working place, no minimum legal protection and abuse of elderly female. Crime against single working women is due to the lack of infrastructure to those who leave their families for working away from home. Any act or omission harmful to the society and punishable by law amounts to crime [1]. Social violence including forcing the daughter in law for foeticide harms the society [2]. In 1993, The United Nations defined ‘Violence against Women’ in the Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women as an act of gender-based violence resulting in the physical, sexual or psychological harm to women whether occurring in public or private life. [3]

2. TYPES OF CRIMES

Among the enormous amount of crimes against women most prominent are explained below.

- Domestic Violence: Any violence including harassment, maltreatment, brutality, assault, intimidation by way of hitting, kicking, biting, shoving, restraining, throwing etc committed at home by the family members.
- Son Preferences: It results in female infanticide through neglect of girl child without providing nutrition, health care and education.
- Dowry and Early Marriage: Payment of bride money resulting in the dowry deaths and early marriages deprive the girls from the right of education.
- Trafficking: The economic and social conditions of women force them to be pushing to the rackets of trafficking.
- Rape: One quarter of the reported rapes involves girls under the age of 16.
- Sexual Assault within the Marriage: As wife is expected to submit causing many sexual assaults which are difficult to prove without serious injuries.
- Sexual Harassment: Harassment through eve teasing, sexual abuse at workplace is increasing due to the influence of western culture.
- Violence against unorganised Labourers: The discrimination in the payment of wage.
- Female Genital Mutilation: World Health Organization reports about some forms of female genital mutilation and its adverse health hazards by 85 million to 115 million girls and women.
- Pornography: It replicates women as mere receptacles for lust.
- Custodial Violence: Members of custodians violates and commits crimes including rape, assault etc.
- Armed Conflicts: Many innocent women were raped during the armed conflicts.
- Incest: Incest is sexual activity between family members and close relatives. This may include sexual activity between people in a consanguineous relationship (blood relations), or related by affinity, such as members of the same household, step relatives, those related by adoption or marriage, or members of the same clan or lineage.[4]
- Commodification of Women: Women are used as commodities in trafficking with little control over their body and life.
- Female Infanticides and Sex selective Abortions: High masculine sex ratio in India can be attributed to female infanticides and sex-selective abortions.
- Trafficking: Women are forced into prostitution, child labour and exploitation.

- Dowry: A traditional social practice, dowry is the ritual of a bride's family giving cash and/or goods to the family of the groom, as an accompaniment to their giving away the bride. IT emerged to be a cultural phenomena for the people of all castes and class [5]
- Child Marriage: Due to poverty many children below the age of 18 years were married leading to health problems and malnutrition.
- Eve-Teasing: Eve teasing is an act of terror that violates a woman's body, space and self-respect by making women to feel inferior, weak and afraid.
- Acid Attacks: Acid is used to disfigure or kill women against the issues of family feuds, inability to meet dowry demands and for rejection of marriage proposals.

3. CONSTITUTIONAL & LEGAL PROVISIONS ON WOMEN

The principle of gender equality is enshrined in the Indian Constitution in its Preamble, Fundamental Rights, Fundamental Duties and Directive Principles. It not only grants equality to women, but also empowers the State to adopt measures of positive discrimination in favour of women for neutralizing the cumulative socio economic, education and political disadvantages faced by them. Within the framework of a democratic polity, our laws, development policies, Plans and programmes have aimed at women's advancement in different spheres. India has also ratified Convention on Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women in 1993. [6]. Article 14, confers on men and women equal rights and opportunities in political, economic and social sphere. Article 15, prohibits, discrimination against any citizen on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex etc. Article 16, provides for equality of opportunities matters relating to employment or appointment to any office under the state. Article 39(a)(d), mentions policy security of state equality for both men and women the right to a means of livelihood and equal pay for equal work for both men and women. Article 42, Direct the State to make provision for ensuring just and humane conditions of work and maternity relief. Legal provisions such as *Factories Act 1948*: Under this Act, a woman cannot be forced to work beyond 8 hours and prohibits employment of women except between 6 A.M. and 7 P.M. *Maternity Benefit Act 1961*: A Woman is entitled 12 weeks maternity leave with full wages. *The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961*: Under the provisions of this Act demand of dowry either before marriage, during marriage and or after the marriage is an offence. *The Equal Remuneration Act of 1976*: This act provides equal wages for equal work: It provides for the payment of equal wages to both men and women workers for the same work or work of similar nature. It also prohibits discrimination against women in the matter of recruitment. *The Child Marriage Restrain Act of 1976*: This act raises the age for marriage of a girl to 18 years from 15 years and that of a boy to 21 years. *Indian Penal Code*: Section 354 and 509 safeguards the interests of women. *The Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act of 1971*: The Act safeguards women from unnecessary and compulsory abortions. Amendments to Criminal Law 1983, which provides for a punishment of 7 years in ordinary cases and 10 years for custodial rape cases. *73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendment Act* reserved 1/3rd seats in Panchayat and Urban Local Bodies for women. *The National Commission for Women Act, 1990*. The act such as *The Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993*, *Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005*, *Protection of Women against Sexual Harassment at Workplace Bill, 2010*: on November 4, 2010, the Government introduced protection of Women Against Sexual Harassment at Workplace Bill, 2010, which aims at protecting the women at

workplace not only to women employee but also to female clients, customer, students, research scholars in colleges and universities patients in hospitals. The Bill was passed in Lok Sabha on 3.9.2012. Although women may be victims of any of the general crimes such as ‘murder’, ‘robbery’, ‘cheating’, etc. only the crimes which are directed specifically against women are characterised as ‘crimes against women’. Various new legislations have been brought and amendments have been made in existing laws with a view to handle these crimes effectively. These are broadly classified under two categories.

(1) The Crimes under the Indian Penal Code (IPC): Rape (Sec. 376 IPC), Attempt to commit rape (Sec 376/511 IPC), Kidnapping & abduction of women (Section 363,364,364A, 366 IPC), Dowry deaths (Section 304B IPC), Assault on woman with intent to outrage her modesty (Sec. 354 IPC), Sexual harassment (Sec.354A IPC), Assault on woman with intent to outrage her modesty (Sec. 354C IPC), Voyeurism (Sec. 354D IPC), Others, Insult to the modesty of women (Sec. 509 IPC), Cruelty by husband or his relatives, (Sec. 498A IPC), Importation of girl from foreign country (up to 21 years of age) (Sec. 366 B IPC), Abetment of suicide of women (Sec. 306 IPC).

(2) The Crimes under the Special & Local Law: Although all laws are not gender specific, the provisions of law affecting women significantly have been reviewed periodically and amendments carried out to keep pace with the emerging requirements. The gender specific laws for which crime statistics are recorded throughout the country are The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961, The Indecent Representation of Women Prohibition Act, 1986, The Commission of Sati Prevention Act, 1987 , The Protection of women from domestic Violence Act, 2005, The Immoral Traffic Prevention Act, 1956. Empowerment of women guarantees dignified life at the threshold of providing them with social justice. The most effective strategies are likely to be those that support women to organize peer groups and mobilize community resources and public services, including women’s health services. Such approaches enable women to overcome resignation to the legitimacy of the established order are important factor in the perpetuation of imbalances of power between women and men. If women are to implement their reproductive preferences, then it is essential that their empowerment occur not only within their personal spheres, but also in the broader spheres of the community and the state. Although special provisions, affirmative action and reservations in education, employment and political life may have their own advantages, more fundamental than these are creation of a dependable legal framework for protection of their bodily integrity and personal autonomy. A multi-pronged approach for an all-round development of women by setting into service different provisions of the constitution might be more appropriate. The post emergency due process revolution, public interest litigation and judicial activism animating positive dimensions of right to life have made the right to life and due process jurisprudence interestingly more rewarding for women. The declining sex ratio in India amply portrays the discrimination shown towards women at the stage of birth. The crimes against women in India are growing at a rampant speed. Women, irrespective of their class, caste and educational status, are not safe. The lack of any serious effort to rectify the weaknesses in dealing with the crimes against women further. [7] The official statistics showed a declining sex-ratio, health status, literacy rate, work participation rate and political participation among women.

4. CONCLUSION

It is inevitable to create an environment where, women can make independent decisions. Education is the weapon to overcome these inequalities. The semantic meaning of 'crime against women' is direct or indirect physical or mental cruelty to women. Various kinds of violence against women are eve-teasing, molestation, bigamy, fraudulent marriage, adultery and enticement of married women abduction and kidnapping, rape, harassment to women at work ing place, wife beating, dowry death, female child abuse and abuse of elderly female etc. Rape is a crime not only against the person of a woman it is a crime against the entire society. It destroys the entire psychology of a woman and pushes her into deep emotional crisis. Rape is therefore the most hated crime. Crime against women includes any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or private life. Although women may be victims of any of the general crimes such as 'murder', 'robbery', 'cheating', etc, only the crimes which are directed specifically against women are characterized as 'crimes against women'. Various new legislations have been brought and amendments have been made in existing laws with a view to handle these crimes effectively. Only legislation and law enforcement agencies cannot prevent the incident of crime against women. There is need of social awakening and change in the attitude of masses, so that due respect and equal status is given to women. It is a time when the women need to be given her due. This awakening can be brought by education campaign among youth making them aware of existing social evils and the means to eradicate same. Women and feminist organisations are serious in pursuing the constitutional and legal means of attaining justice, both individual and social. All India Democratic Women's Association, Manila Dakshita Samiti and Delhi Domestic Women's Forum have been remarkably successful in lawyering for justice to women suggests the need for consolidating the gains of concerted efforts of women in future. It determined to take constitutional litigation as a sword of remedies with continuous, systematic and well coordinated efforts. Extension of legal literacy and legal clinical service for women with the assistance of lawyers and law teachers goes a long way in this direction. Free and Compulsory education, Freedom to hold high offices, Political rights to franchise and contest in elections, Spouses sharing a common social life in cities are the recent trends.[8] . Almost every woman has experienced the feeling of being mistreated, trivialized, kept out, put down, ignored, assaulted, laughed at or discriminated against because of her gender.[9]. Many evil customs and traditions stepped in which enslaved the women and tied them to the boundaries of the house. [10]. Humiliation, rape, kidnapping, molestation, dowry death, torture, wife-beating etc.have grown up over the years. [11]

REFERENCES

- [1] State Council of Educational Research and Training (2009). Text book of Sociology, Vidya Bhavana, Poojappura, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala ,240-242
- [2] Awadhesh Kumar Singh & Jayanta Choudhury (2012). 'Violence against Women and Children-Issues and Concerns', Serials Publications, New Delhi, 1
- [3] Guruappa Naid, (2011). 'Violence Against Women in India' , Serials Publications, New Delhi, 23

- [4] Rape, Abuse and Incest National Network (RAINN) (2009). 'Incest'. Oxford University Press, Visited on August 27, 2013).
- [5] Banerjee, Priya R. (2014) 'Dowry in 21st-Century India: The Socio-cultural face of Exploitation'. *Trauma, Violence and Abuse* 15.1, Sage Premier. Web. 01 Apr. 2015.
- [6] India, Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (2012), *Women and Men in India* 14th Issue, xiii
- [7] Manikamma Nagindrappa, M K Radhika, (2013). 'Women Exploitation in Indian Modern Society, *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 3 (2), ISSN 2250-3153
- [8] M.D.Pradeep & Deeksha (2016). 'Multi-Dimensional Approach For Empowerment - Effective Strategies To Face Problems And Challenges Of Women In India', *International Journal Of Scientific Research And Modern Education* I(I).
- [9] Rebecca Walker, 'Becoming the Third Wave, ¶from Ms. Magazine, in Leslie L. Heywood' (ed.) (2006). *The Women's Movement Today', An Encyclopedia of Third Wave Feminism* 6, Greenwood Press, U.S.A.
- [10] Aruna Goel (2004). 'Violence and Protective Measures for Women Development and Empowerment', Deep & Deep Publications, New Delhi, 3-4.
- [11] Awadhesh Kumar Singh and Jayanta Choudhury (2012). 'Violence Against Women & Children-Issues & Concerns, Serials Publication, New Delhi, 1